

Performance evaluation of active dosimeters for area workplace and individual monitoring based on historical and aggregated calibration data

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ABSTRACT

Background: Dosimeter type-testing and verification, in addition to regular calibration, ensures the acquisition of high quality dosimetry data and optimization of radiation protection.

Aim: Historical and aggregated calibration data of active dosimeters for individual and area workplace monitoring from several Standard Dosimetry Calibration Laboratories was collected and evaluated in terms of variation in response due to radiation-based influence quantities. These data can be used to support future update and harmonization of type testing standards.

Methods: Dosimeter performance was examined in a wide range of dose rates, covering several orders of magnitude within the measurement ranges, and from 33.3 keV to 1.25 MeV photon energies, respectively. The results were evaluated against limits of variation defined in type testing standards IEC 61526:2024 and IEC 60846-1:2009 for active personal and active ambient dosimeters, respectively.

Results: Most commonly used dosimeters complied with the standard requirements, with some state-of-the-art models exhibiting excellent performance and small response variations within standard stated limits, even beyond the minimum rated ranges. However, some units had pronounced variation in response, up to +68 % for active personal dosimeters and +75 % for active ambient dosimeters. Additionally, devices with inappropriate energy compensation were identified, having an over-response up to +650 %.

Conclusion: These findings confirm the importance of type testing of dosimeter models, along with verification and regular calibration of individual units. Performance indicators showcase that most dosimeters comply with the standards, while some behaved far better, allowing for possibility of proposing a category of radiation protection field instruments with lower uncertainties.

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1. Introduction

Dosimeters which are used for radiation protection of exposed workers in various ionizing radiation practices, spanning from industrial and nuclear technology applications to medical radiation diagnostic and therapy applications, are based on different detector technologies. Nowadays, radiation protection dosimeters which are used for individual or area monitoring, can be classified into active electronic dosimeters, passive dosimetry systems and hybrid dosimeters. Active dosimeters can be realized by using gas-based or solid-state detectors of different active volume materials and geometries (Pavelić et al., 2020; Vanhavere & Van Hoey, 2022). All these dosimeter types can be used to acquire legal dosimetry data. Even when no legal metrological control is implemented, it is good practice for these devices to be calibrated and, preferably, to have well-defined metrological characteristics (Ginjaume et al., 2006).

Quality of the dosimetry data acquired during monitoring activities depends on correct use, appropriate measurement methods and good dosimeter performance. This can be achieved by dosimeter type testing and by performing regular calibration and/or verification of each dosimeter unit individually. The requirements on dosimeter performance testing depend on the national regulations and are country specific.

Type testing is performed through evaluation of dosimeter performance according to test procedures and methods defined in the relevant standards, e.g., International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) standards (IEC, 2009; IEC, 2024). These tests consider effects of different influence quantities (radiation-based influence quantities such as photon energy, environment-based influence quantities related to air density, electromagnetic and mechanical influence quantities, and others). Dosimeter verification consists of specifically tailored tests that can be performed instead of, or in addition to, regular periodic calibration in the dosimetry calibration laboratories, such as Secondary Standard Dosimetry Laboratories (SSDL).

Type testing standards issued by the IEC subcommittee SC 45B provide methods of testing, minimum rated ranges of various influence quantities as well as limits of variation in dosimeter response within which the tested dosimeter must remain to exhibit compliance. IEC 61526:2024 defines performance requirements and methods of testing active personal dosimeters (APDs) (IEC, 2024). On the other hand, performance requirements and test methods of active ambient dosimeters (AADs) are defined by several different IEC standards, stressing the need for harmonization in this area of radiation protection (Kržanović et al., 2022). The most commonly used standard for testing of AADs in the workplace is IEC 60846-1:2009 (IEC, 2009). Currently, there are no standards that provide clear requirements for AADs used for environmental monitoring.

Dosimeter calibration is usually performed in reference radionuclide radiation fields, with either Cs-137 or Co-60, which have discrete gamma emission lines. Even though dosimeters usually display good performance in these radiation fields, when exposed to radiation fields of different energies (especially in the low-energy range), their performance can be inadequate and unreliable (Boziari & Hourdakis, 2007; Kržanović et al., 2017; Živanović et al., 2022; Đaletić et al., 2025; Vlahović et al., 2025). In some cases, radiation protection dosimeters can have a very pronounced over-response at low-photon energies or, on the contrary, have very low sensitivity, both of which are mainly related to the dosimeter design limitations (e.g., shape and material of the dosimeter or probe housing, detector type, design or absence of energy compensation filter) (Vanhavere & Van Hoey, 2022). Research performed by Vlahović et al. (2026) assessed active ambient and personal dosimeter performance in a wide range of photon energies, angles of incidence and dose rate values, evaluating thereby the possibility of introducing two distinct dosimeter classes. Presented results highlighted that some state-of-the-art dosimeters have excellent performance and small variations in response, however, in some cases more pronounced

variations were noted for low photon energies and high angles of incidence.

In this research, aggregated calibration data from several SSDLs was collected to conduct performance analysis of commonly used state-of-the-art active radiation protection dosimeters, as a part of the 22NRM07 GuideRadPROS joint research project (GuideRadPROS, 2026). The dataset comprises a substantial number of calibration results performed in National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes (DIs), providing thereby a broad basis for performance evaluation. While there are many papers evaluating specific dosimeter models, this paper presents the evaluation of performance on a larger scale covering a wide range of dosimeter models, used in many European countries for ambient and personal monitoring. Therefore, analysis of dosimeter performance based on historical calibration data, with respect to the literature and the current requirements set by the IEC type testing standards, would present a solid indicator on whether the harmonization and update of type testing standards is necessary considering the observed dosimeter performance. The presented data could also provide valuable input for defining national criteria for dosimeter verification and type testing. Additionally, knowledge on dosimeter performance would lead to a better understanding of related measurement uncertainties in radiation protection dosimetry practice.

2. Materials and methods

Historical and aggregated calibration data in reference radiation fields were collected from several SSDLs. Calibration of active dosimeters is performed in reference gamma and X-ray radiation fields established according to ISO 4037:2019 (ISO, 2019a). Gamma-ray radiation fields based on Cs-137 (S-Cs, 662 keV mean photon energy) and Co-60 (S-Co, 1.25 MeV mean photon energy) radioisotopes, are commonly used for radiation protection dosimeter calibration. Collected data on dosimeter calibration includes the narrow-spectra X-ray radiation qualities (termed as N-series) as well. These radiation qualities are highly filtered, with the homogeneity coefficient (ratio of the first and second half-value layer) close to unity. This makes them particularly useful for energy dependence testing of dosimeters. Aggregated data on dosimeter calibration in the N-series radiation qualities cover the mean photon energy range from 33 keV to 165 keV, represented by the following radiation qualities with their respective mean photon energies: N-40 (33.3 keV), N-60 (47.9 keV), N-80 (65.2 keV), N-100 (83.3 keV), N-120 (100 keV), N-150 (118 keV), and N-200 (165 keV); (ISO, 2019a).

2.1. Secondary Standard Dosimetry Laboratories

Seven European SSDLs provided historical data on calibration of radiation protection dosimeters. These laboratories are either NMIs or DIs, with Quality Management Systems established and recognized according to the ISO/IEC 17025 (ISO/IEC, 2017). All the SSDLs perform calibrations in line with procedures defined in ISO 4037:2019 (ISO, 2019a; ISO, 2019b) and ISO 29961:2012 (ISO, 2012).

Reference values for air kerma are realized by secondary standard ionization chambers (e.g., PTW 32002 or similar) and then typically, the reference values of operational quantities are derived based on conversion coefficients from the ISO 4037:2019 standard (ISO, 2019b). It is possible to obtain reference values of operational quantities directly by utilizing special chambers designed to measure these quantities (Xu & Zhao, 2021).

In the radionuclide reference radiation fields (S-Cs and S-Co), known radiation field method (IAEA, 2000) is commonly used, where the reference dose (rate) values are measured and validated at different source-to-detector distances with a reference (secondary) standard. Dose rates can then be calculated at any distance and point of time (considering the radioactive decay law and dependence of dose rate on the square of distance). A calibration method with monitor chamber (e.

g., PTW 34014 or similar) is commonly used for X-ray N-series reference fields. In addition, substitution method with or without monitor chamber can be used for any radiation quality. In general, while being more time consuming, the substitution method yields lower total measurement uncertainties, compared to other methods (IAEA, 2000). In all SSDLs, X-ray generators of similar characteristics and X-ray tube voltage ranges are being used to establish the N-series radiation qualities. A schematic of the setup is presented in Fig. 1.

In general, the measurement uncertainty budget of the reference value includes several measurement uncertainty components related to the determination of the reference (conventional true) value and the reference radiation field properties. The principal contributor to the measurement uncertainty budget is the conversion coefficient from air kerma to the operational quantity, since conversion coefficients are typically obtained from the ISO 4037:2019 standard (ISO, 2019b). For matched reference radiation fields, the expanded measurement uncertainty for the conversion coefficient yields a 4.0 % contribution, with a $k = 2$ coverage factor. Other significant contributions include reference chamber calibration factor, reference chamber stability, field homogeneity, deviations from the inverse square law, monitor chamber energy dependence etc.

Each of the SSDLs has defined procedures for uncertainty calculation in accordance with ISO/IEC 17025 (ISO/IEC, 2017), ISO 4037 (ISO, 2019b) and "Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement" (Joint committee for guides in metrology JCGM, 2008). While the uncertainty budgets differ between the laboratories, principal uncertainty components are the same in most cases, and combined uncertainty is similar for all participating SSDLs. A detailed description of the uncertainty budgets of five of the calibration laboratories that provided the aggregated data was published in the report of a recent Supplementary Comparison (Živanović et al., 2023). While some laboratories that provided the data have primary standards, secondary methods are used to calibrate field class dosimeters for area and individual monitoring, resulting in a similar SSDL-level uncertainty budget. Combined measurement uncertainty of the reference value for the methods used for dosimeter calibration can be conservatively set to 5 % ($k = 2$) for all participating SSDLs. Consequentially, the total measurement uncertainty of approximately 7 % ($k = 2$) is derived for the relative response. Correlations between the absolute response values which were used to derive the relative response were considered negligible in this study. In the energy dependence test, different values of conversion coefficients and calibration coefficients are used, while in the case of non-linearity

test, even though the same radiation quality is used to determine relative response, sources of different activities are often used to achieve a wide range of dose rates needed, so even though the correlations may exist they are considered negligible in this study.

Since the aggregated data was collected from several standard calibration laboratories, differences between the laboratories slightly increased the spread of the presented results. However, these variations are significantly less pronounced than the standard IEC limits, which can be seen from (Živanović et al., 2023).

2.2. Dosimeters for individual monitoring

Active personal dosimeters (APDs) used for individual monitoring analysed in this paper cover a range of portable devices that are mostly based on semiconductor detectors (such as silicon diodes) and gas-filled Geiger-Müller (G-M) counter detectors. The list of selected APDs, which were included in this study, their properties in terms of dose rate measurement range, photon energy range, and the collected sample size for each of the dosimeter models, are presented in Table 1.

2.3. Dosimeters for ambient monitoring

Active ambient dosimeters (AADs) are used in the monitoring of workplaces (in both industrial, scientific, medical and other applications) and in the environmental monitoring in radiation monitoring networks. Various detectors are employed for the realization of AADs, including gas-filled detectors (G-M counters, proportional counter tubes (PC) and high pressurized ionization chambers (HP IC)), semiconductor detectors and scintillators (inorganic such as CsI(Tl) and NaI(Tl), plastic/organic and other), out of which G-M counter-based devices are most utilized (Čeklić et al., 2014). AAD models, with their respective manufacturer-stated specifications and sample sizes, are presented in Table 2.

2.4. Radiation-based influence quantities

Dosimeter performance requirements are defined in IEC 61526:2024 (IEC, 2024) for APDs used for individual monitoring, and IEC 60846-1:2009 (IEC, 2009) for AADs used in regular area workplace monitoring. These standards define test methods and reference/standard test conditions. Limits of variation of the dosimeter response are also provided for a specific range of values for each influence quantity (minimum rated ranges). Minimum rated range represents the range of values of an influence quantity for which the variation of dosimeter response should be within the limits of variation in order to comply with the type testing standard.

Indication of radiation protection dosimeters can significantly differ from the true value of the operational quantity due to effects of radiation-based influence quantities. The most important ones are photon energy, angle of incidence, and dose (rate). Influence quantities represent physical quantities that are not the subject of measurement but can influence the measurement result (IEC, 2009; IEC, 2024).

The absolute response of a dosimeter is defined as the quotient of the value measured by the dosimeter, corrected for background indication, and the reference (conventional true) value determined by a standard instrument with established traceability. Absolute response, R_i , is presented with the following equation:

$$R_i(X) = \frac{G_i(X)}{C_i(X)} \quad (1)$$

where $G_i(X)$ represents the measured value, and $C_i(X)$ the conventional true value of the operational quantity for the specific value of an influence quantity X .

Relative response is defined as the ratio of the absolute response under certain conditions $R_i(X)$, and the absolute response under refer-

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the experimental setup: XRT - X-ray tube; K1, K2 and K3 - apertures; F1 and F2 - additional filtration; M - monitor ionization chamber; d - source-to-detector distance; P - ISO slab phantom (used with APDs); S - positioning support (low Z material); D_A - Active Ambient Dosimeter; D_P - Active Personal Dosimeter.

Table 1

Manufacturer specifications of APDs related to detector type, dose rate measurement range, and photon energy range. Sample size for each dosimeter model is included.

Detector type	Manufacturer	Model	Dose rate measurement range		Photon energy range		Sample size <i>n</i>	APD No.
			Min [$\mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$]	Max [Sv h^{-1}]	Min [keV]	Max [MeV]		
G-M counter	Automess	ADOS	0.1	1	65	3	2	APD1
		Alados	0.05	1	65	3	1	APD2
	Graetz	GPD150G	0.1	1	55	1.3	5	APD3
		GPD100	0.1	1	48	2	2	APD4
		ED150	0.05	1.5	55	3	2	APD5
	Polimaster	PM1610/PM1610B	0.1	10	20	10	72	APD6
	Technical Associates	PDA200+	0.1	0.1	40	1.3	1	APD7
	Tracerco	T414-2	0.1	0.1	33	1.25	2	APD8
Silicon semiconductor	Atomtex	AT3509A	0.1	1	30	10	1	APD9
	Hitachi Aloka	PDM 227C-SH	1	0.1	20	0.2	3	APD10
	MGP Instruments	DMC 2000	0.1	10	20	6	19	APD11
	Mirion	DMC 3000	1	10	15	10	18	APD12
	Rados	RAD60	5	3	60	6	3	APD13
	Saphymo	DoxSi-2G	0.5	5	50	7	1	APD14
		Saphydose	0.5	5	50	7	11	APD15
	Thermo Fisher	EPDMk2	0.1	4	15	10	28	APD16
		EPD TruDose	1	2	16	1.5	23	APD17

Table 2

Manufacturer specifications of AADs related to detector type, dose rate measurement range and photon energy range. Sample size for each dosimeter model is included.

Detector type	Manufacturer	Model	Dose rate measurement range		Photon energy range		Sample size <i>n</i>	AAD No.	
			Min [$\mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$]	Max [mSv h^{-1}]	Min [keV]	Max [MeV]			
High pressurized ionization chamber	Fluke	451P	0	50	25	1.25	6	AAD1	
Proportional counter	Thermo Fisher	FH40G-L10	0.01	100	30	4.4	16	AAD2	
G-M counter	Atomtex	AT6130	0.1	10	20	3	10	AAD3	
		AT6130A	0.1	10	50	3	4	AAD4	
		AT6130C	0.1	1	50	3	4	AAD5	
		AT1117M ^a	1	10 (100) ^b	60	3	10	AAD6	
		BDPS02	0.1	30	20	3	3	AAD7	
		6150 AD6/H	0.1	10	60	1.3	12	AAD8	
	Automess	6150 AD1/H	1	1000	45	2.6	10	AAD9	
		Bertin	Minitrace	0.5	10	42	2.8	12	AAD10
	Canberra	Radiagem 2000	0.01	100	40	1.5	19	AAD11	
	Ecotest	Terra MKS-05	0.1	1	50	3	6	AAD12	
	Gamma Scout	Gamma Scout	0.01	5	N/A	N/A	1	AAD13	
	Graetz	X5C+	1	20	40	1.3	5	AAD14	
	Joy-it	JT-RAD01	0	10	48	1.5	1	AAD15	
	Kata-Electronics	DGM-1500 TURVA	0.01	100	45	1.25	3	AAD16	
	Mirion	RDS-30	0.01	100	48	3	3	AAD17	
		Colibri	0.1	1	59	1.5	2	AAD18	
	PCE Instruments	PCE-RAM10	0.01	1	20	N/A	1	AAD19	
	Polimaster	PM1208M	0.01	10	60	1.5	4	AAD20	
		PM1203	0.1	2	60	1.5	2	AAD21	
		PM1603B	1	10	48	3	7	AAD22	
	Radex	RD1706	0.05	1	30	3	1	AAD23	
	Rados	RDS-120	0.05	100	50	1.25	3	AAD24	
	S.E. International	Digilert 100	0.01	1	10	1.3	1	AAD25	
		Inspector+	0.1	1	10	1.3	1	AAD26	
	Thermo Fisher	RadEye G10	0.5	100	50	3	6	AAD27	
	TRF	GM Rady	0.1	20	N/A	N/A	2	AAD28	
	UNI-T	UT334A	0.01	500	N/A	N/A	1	AAD29	
	VINS	DMRZ-M15	0.1	1	59	1.3	18	AAD30	
	G-M counter	Raysafe	452	0	0.02	20	1	2	AAD31
			Silicon semiconductor	20	1000	20	5		
Scintillator	NaI (TI)	Atomtex	BDKG03	0.03	0.3	50	3	3	AAD32
	CsI (TI)	Polimaster	PM1703GNAlI	0.1	0.3	33	3	1	AAD33
Scintillator	Plastic	Atomtex	BDKG04	0.05	10 000	15 (25) ^c	10 (3) ^c	3	AAD34
	NaI (TI)	Ortec	RadEaglet	0.01	0.25	15	3	1	AAD35
G-M counter	/		250	1000	45	1.5			

^a AT1117M has an internal detector, but it can also be used with several different external probes (such as BDKG03, BDKG04, or BDPS02). The data collected for the main unit and the individual probes are evaluated separately.

^b Measurement range upper limit for AT1117M can differ between the processing unit versions.

^c Photon energy range in parentheses applies to the use of a compensation filter cap applied on the probe.

ence conditions, $R_0(X_0)$, presented with the following equation:

$$r_i(X) = \frac{R_i(X)}{R_0(X_0)} \quad (2)$$

During the examination of the effect of a certain influence quantity, values of all other influence quantities are set to their reference values or otherwise need to be corrected for. In the case influence quantities are strongly correlated (e.g., photon energy and angle of incidence), the test is performed simultaneously for these quantities.

2.5. Acceptability criteria

Dosimeter compliance with IEC standards is achieved by comparing the dosimeter response with acceptability criteria (usually limits of variation) for a certain influence quantity. In a previous research, conducted within the scope of the 22NRM07 GuideRadPROS project, introduction of two distinct dosimeter classes was proposed, with more strict limits of variation defined for Class A AADs and APDs (Vlahović et al., 2026). Current limits of variation and minimum rated ranges defined in the IEC 60846-1:2009 (IEC, 2009) and IEC 61526:2024 (IEC, 2024), as well as the newly proposed limits are summarized in Table 3.

The IEC limits of variation (in terms of relative response) (IEC, 2009; IEC, 2024) are enlarged by the uncertainty of the conventional true value (considering the correlations, where applicable). The dosimeters fulfil the requirements if the following inequality is satisfied:

$$r_{min} - U_C \leq \frac{\bar{G}_i}{\bar{G}_{r,0}} \frac{C_{r,0}}{C_i} \leq r_{max} + U_C \quad (3)$$

where, r_{min} and r_{max} represent the lower and the upper limit of variation, respectively, enlarged with the combined expanded measurement uncertainty of the reference value, U_C . The product of ratios $\frac{\bar{G}_i}{\bar{G}_{r,0}} \cdot \frac{C_{r,0}}{C_i}$ represents the relative response under certain irradiation conditions $r_i(X)$ (Eq. (2)).

In this study the limits of variation were expanded with the reference value combined measurement uncertainty of 7 % ($k = 2$) for the performed tests. The IEC standards define the maximum allowed combined measurement uncertainty of the reference value at 10 % ($k = 2$) (IEC, 2009; IEC, 2024).

2.5.1. Linearity (dose rate dependence)

Aggregated calibration data obtained from dosimeter calibrations performed in the S-Cs or S-Co radiation fields over multiple orders of magnitude were used for the performance evaluation in terms of response non-linearity. As per the IEC standards, the evaluation of non-linearity should be done in the reference radiation quality, S-Cs (662 keV) (IEC, 2009; IEC, 2024). In cases where it was not possible to cover the whole instrument measurement range using the reference irradiation condition (S-Cs), the range was extended by using S-Co (mean photon energy 1.25 MeV). Non-linearity results acquired in the S-Co radiation field were corrected for the energy dependence of the response by using Eq. (2) to determine the $r_{Co60}(E)$ correction factors.

The reference conditions for the non-linearity test were selected for APDs and AADs based on the standard test conditions defined in their respective standards (IEC, 2009; IEC, 2024). In the case of APDs, the

selected reference personal dose equivalent rate was.

500 $\mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, whereas for AADs, the ambient dose equivalent rate of 50 $\mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was chosen.

It should be noted that dose rates below 1 $\mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ are out of the scope of ISO 4037:2019 (ISO, 2019a), where contributions from the background radiation to the measured value are not negligible. Additionally, to acquire the reference values at very low dose rates, dosimeters based on scintillator detectors are typically used. Consequentially, the measurement uncertainty of the reference values is increased.

2.5.2. Energy dependence

Aggregated calibration data from N-series and S-Co radiation qualities were used to evaluate energy dependence of dosimeter response. Relative energy response was determined by normalizing the absolute response at each radiation quality, $R_i(E)$, to the absolute response determined for the reference condition, E_0 , being S-Cs (mean photon energy 662 keV). This radiation quality is defined as the reference condition for energy dependence evaluation, since it has a discreet gamma emission line with high emission probability. During the energy dependence test, the dose rate was kept constant for all radiation qualities. The selected dose rate value depends on the dosimeter measurement range. For all APDs the dose rate of 2 $\text{mSv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was used for all radiation qualities. For AADs with the upper limit of the measurement range above 10 $\text{mSv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, the same dose rate as for APDs (2 $\text{mSv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) was used. On the other hand, for AADs with a smaller measurement range, the reference dose rate of 300 $\mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was selected.

Both IEC 61526:2024 (IEC, 2024) and IEC 60846-1:2009 (IEC, 2009) define two minimum rated ranges for the energy dependence test, depending on the intended dosimeter application. The first one, from 80 keV to 1.25 MeV pertains to general workplaces and the use of high energy X-rays, and gamma sources (e.g., industrial applications of ionizing radiation), whereas the second one, from 20 keV to 150 keV, is related to low-energy X-ray radiation applications such as diagnostic radiology applications.

3. Results and discussion

The results of APD and AAD relative response in terms of non-linearity and energy dependence are presented in Figs. 2–10. Figs. 2–5 present non-linearity of APDs and AADs, Figs. 6–9 energy dependence of APDs and AADs. In the case when data for more than 10 different units, of the same dosimeter model, was available, the results are presented as box plots and each data point represents a relative response value of an individual dosimeter unit. In this way, the differences between individual units of dosimeter types, which were identified as most commonly used in different countries, were compared. On the contrary, when data for less than 10 units was collected for a certain dosimeter type, the average relative response for the sample was calculated. Special attention was given to certain models of active ambient dosimeters which displayed significant under and over-response, in terms of their relative energy response. Fig. 10 presents the energy dependence of

Table 3

Acceptability criteria defined by the IEC standards for type testing of radiation protection dosimeters (IEC, 2009; IEC, 2024), and Class A proposed limits (Vlahović et al., 2026).

Standard	Influence quantity		Energy dependence	
	Non-linearity			
	Minimum rated range	Limits of variation	Minimum rated range	Limits of variation
IEC 61526:2024 Class A ^a	All orders of magnitude including measurement range limits and 30% of each order of magnitude	$r(H)$, 0.87 – 1.18 $r(H)$, 0.91 – 1.11	(80 keV; 1.5 MeV) (20 keV; 150 keV)	$r(E)$, 0.71 – 1.67 $r(E)$, 0.83 – 1.25
IEC 60846-1:2009 Class A ^a	At least three orders of magnitude including 20%, 40%, and 80% of each order of magnitude	$r(H)$, 0.85 – 1.22	(80 keV; 1.5 MeV) (20 keV; 150 keV)	$r(E)$, 0.71 – 1.67
		$r(H)$, 0.91 – 1.11		$r(E)$, 0.83 – 1.25

^a Class A limits of variation are not a part of the current type testing standards

Fig. 2. Non-Linearity of active personal dosimeter (APD) response, $n > 10$, normalized to the $500 \mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$ reference dose rate: a) APD6; b) APD11; c) APD12; d) APD15; e) APD16; f) APD17. The limits of variation (-13% ; $+18\%$) in terms of relative response are displayed (IEC, 2024).

these dosimeters.

3.1. Non-linearity (dose rate dependence)

Non-linearity of the APD response is presented in Figs. 2 and 3. In general, APDs have displayed good performance, and most of them have their relative response within the standard stated limits of variation (-13% , $+18\%$) (IEC, 2024). With the increase of the dose rate value the dosimeters exhibit a more uniform response, and the largest deviations from the reference response can be noted for the lowest dose rate values, as is the case with APD6, APD12 and APD17. For some dosimeters, those dose rate values are on the lower limit of their measurement range, which could explain the large distribution in the response values for the same dosimeter model. Additionally, detector sensitivity and count-rate statistics impact its response.

Out of all the tested dosimeters APD6 presented the largest dispersion of results across the tested dose rate range. Additionally, among APDs presented in Fig. 2, APD6 is the only G-M counter based dosimeter, and the only one whose performance characteristics were evaluated for a dose rate value below $1 \mu\text{Sv} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$. The observed distribution in relative responses can be attributed to the inherent background of individual units and the large sample size, which includes new units of the dosimeter model, as well as older units, whose properties may have deteriorated over time. Overall, this dosimeter model exhibited good performance, and the majority of units satisfy the standard stated requirements (IEC, 2024). It was observed that APD11, APD12 and APD16, which utilize the same detector technology (silicon semi-conductors) follow a similar trend in terms of relative response. For the lowest dose rate ($5 \mu\text{Sv} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) a slight under-response is observed for majority of units, while on the high dose rate of $5 \text{mSv} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, the relative

Fig. 3. Non-Linearity of active personal dosimeter (APD) response, $n < 10$, in the dose rate range from $0.5 \mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$ to 50mSv h^{-1} , normalized to the $500 \mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$ reference dose rate. The limits of variation (-13% ; $+18\%$) in terms of relative response are displayed (IEC, 2024).

response of most dosimeters is close to unity. Two dosimeters, APD15 and APD17, exhibited excellent performance, having a uniform response across all tested dose rates, with a variation in their relative response of approximately 10%. Therefore, they can be utilized in various exposure scenarios and ionizing radiation practices, especially in the case of high-dose rate exposures, such as industrial radiography and nuclear technology applications (e.g., nuclear engineering and waste disposal facilities).

Hupe et al. (2019) tested the performance of six active personal dosimeters in standardised continuous and pulsed radiation fields. Dosimeter non-linearity was evaluated in a wide range of dose rates, exceeding the manufacturer specifications. The presented results complement the findings of this study, for the high dose rate values.

AAD non-linearity response is presented in Figs. 4 and 5. AADs exhibited good performance across the examined range in accordance with the standard stated limits of variation (-15% , $+22\%$) (IEC, 2009). As with APDs, the variation in the response of some dosimeters decreases with the increase in dose rate, and is closer to unity. The largest deviation from the reference response, -33.5% , was noted for a single unit of the dosimeter model AAD8. However, this value is at the lower end of the instrument measurement range, which could be a contributing factor to the dosimeters under-response. It was observed that scintillator based dosimeters displayed small variations in their relative response, especially for low dose rate values, which is consistent with their intended use. Similar behaviour was noted for AAD1, which is a high pressurized ionization chamber. On the contrary, AAD31, which utilizes a dual-based detector system (Table 2), for the lower dose rate values, below $20 \mu\text{Sv} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, exhibited over-response, which could be attributed to the count rate statistics and detector sensitivity of the G-M counter. However, when the detector switches to a semiconductor based one, a more stable response can be observed. Since this dosimeter incorporates two different detector technologies it is important to evaluate the effects of influence quantities on the performance of each detector separately.

Larger dispersion had been noted for lower dose rate values, which could be attributed to the instruments inherent background radiation level, electrical noise and built-in computation algorithms (Morosh et al., 2021). This is especially significant when AADs are used for environmental monitoring, where various energies at very low dose rates can be encountered. This result stresses the importance of individual dosimeter verification (Lee & Burgess, 2014). In this way, individual units which may have malfunctions, either due to aging of the

device, improper maintenance or damage to the detection volume (e.g. gas leakage) can be identified.

Previously conducted research proposed the idea for updating current IEC type testing standards by introducing two distinct dosimeter classes, which differentiate dosimeters by their performance. Class A dosimeters would pertain to more strict limits of variation, while in the case of Class B they would remain as they currently are (Vlahović et al., 2026). For the non-linearity test the newly proposed limits of variation for Class A dosimeters would be from -9% , up to $+11\%$ (Table 3). Based on the presented results it can be observed that most dosimeter models fulfil the proposed criteria, apart from some AADs and APDs at lower dose rate values.

3.2. Energy dependence

APD energy response dependence is presented in Figs. 6 and 7. Excellent performance in terms of relative response was observed across the entire photon energy range in accordance with their respective manufacturer-stated specifications (Table 2), as well as standard stated limits of variation (-29% , $+67\%$) (IEC, 2024). Notably, APD17 displayed a steady and uniform response, with an average deviation of $\sim 10\%$ from the reference response, which is excellent performance, considering that photon energy can have a great impact on the measured value.

APD7 exhibited an under-response of -48.1% at N-40 radiation quality (33.3 keV mean photon energy), however this radiation quality is beyond the manufacturer stated measurement range. Similarly, APD4 showed an under-response -37.6% for the N-60 radiation quality (47.9 keV mean photon energy), which is at the lower end of the instrument's measurement range. These findings are consistent with previous studies that also reported deterioration in dosimeter response for low photon energies (Calvacante et al., 2025; Garzon et al., 2018). The maximum deviation from the reference response of $+67.4\%$ was noted for APD9, for the radiation quality N-80 (65.2 keV mean photon energy). Even so, if the expanded limits of variation are taken into consideration, this dosimeter model complies with the standard requirements (IEC, 2024).

AAD energy response dependence is presented in Figs. 8 and 9. It was observed that AADs satisfy the standard stated limits of variation, down to the N-40 radiation quality (IEC, 2009). The differences in the response variation for each dosimeter model could be attributed to their individual energy compensation, since most of them utilize G-M counter based detector technology (Kržanović et al., 2019; Morosh et al., 2021;

Fig. 4. Non-Linearity of active ambient dosimeter (AAD) response, $n > 10$, normalized to the $50 \mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$ reference dose rate: a) AAD2; b) AAD3; c) AAD6; d) AAD8; e) AAD9; f) AAD10; g) AAD11; h) AAD30. The limits of variation (-15% ; $+22\%$) in terms of relative response are displayed (IEC, 2009).

Fig. 5. Non-linearity of active ambient dosimeter (AAD) response, $n < 10$, in the dose rate range from $0.5 \mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$ to 100mSv h^{-1} , normalized to the $50 \mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$ reference dose rate: a) AAD1-18; b) AAD20-34. The limits of variation (-13% ; $+18\%$) in terms of relative response are displayed (IEC, 2024).

Fig. 6. Energy dependence of active personal dosimeter (APD) response, $n > 10$, in the range from 33 keV (N-40) to 1.25 MeV (S-Co), normalized to the S-Cs radiation quality (662 keV): a) APD6; b) APD11; c) APD12; d) APD16; e) APD17. The limits of variation (-29% ; $+67\%$) in terms of relative energy response are displayed (IEC, 2024).

Fig. 7. Energy dependence of active personal dosimeter (APD) response, $n < 10$, in the range from 33 keV (N-40) to 1.25 MeV (S-Co), normalized to the S-Cs radiation quality (662 keV). The limits of variation (-29% ; $+67\%$) in terms of relative energy response are displayed (IEC, 2024).

Čeklić et al., 2014). Some dosimeters, such as AAD8 and AAD11, have a relatively stable response across all photon energies. Whereas, some devices have a lower response for low photon energy radiation qualities, such as N-40 (33.3 keV mean photon energy), which should be taken into consideration depending on the concrete use of the instrument. This could be attributed to the dosimeter design, energy compensation material and associated filtering material used. The maximum deviations from the reference response of approximately $+75\%$ were noted for AAD6 (at N-120) and AAD20 (at N-100).

In previously conducted research, with a goal of updating type testing standards, adjusted limits of variation were proposed for Class A dosimeters (Vlahović et al., 2026). For the relative energy response, the proposed limits were set from -17% to $+25\%$ (Table 3). Not many devices included in this study comply with the stricter criteria in the evaluated photon energy range. However, some dosimeter models presented excellent performance characteristics, such as APD17, which is a state-of-the-art semiconductor-based dosimeter, AAD14, which is based on a G-M counter, and AAD31, which represents a state-of-the-art dual detector system. These devices showed a stable response, and small variations with photon energy. It should be noted that the historical calibration data contained information on dosimeter performance in terms of their energy dependence, while the IEC limits (as well as the proposed Class A limits) pertain to both energy and angular dependence of dosimeters.

Angle of incidence accompanied with photon energy can have a most significant impact on the dosimeter performance. Although angular dependence is also present at high photon energies (e.g., encountered in radiotherapy applications) (Alipour et al., 2023; Hosseini Aghdam et al., 2023), this effect is especially pronounced in low photon energy fields at high angles of incidence (Calvacante et al., 2025; Kržanović et al., 2017; Vlahović et al., 2025). Such radiation conditions are typically encountered in diagnostic radiology applications of ionizing radiation. Furthermore, in the case of environmental monitoring angular dependence can have a significant contribution, due to specific irradiation conditions. Additional data on dosimeter performance was obtained in the scope of 22NRM07 GuideRadPROS project in order to address the identified gaps in data (Vlahović et al., 2026).

Based on aggregated calibration data collected from SSDs which participated in this study, it was observed that certain AAD models exhibited significant under and over-response. The energy dependence response curve of these dosimeters is presented in Fig. 10. Almost all of these dosimeters displayed over-response ranging from $+87.2\%$ up to

$+650\%$. Additionally, the maximum under-response of -91.1% was recorded for one of the devices in this group. Over-response was particularly prominent in the lower photon energy range, indicating inadequate energy compensation (Kržanović et al., 2019; Li et al., 2025; Morosh et al., 2021). The presented results emphasize the importance of dosimeter type testing. Use of low-cost devices, with poor dosimetry characteristics or use of devices which are not intended for dosimetry applications (e.g., radioisotope identification devices, or radiation alarm monitors/indicators), can lead to misleading conclusions regarding personal or workplace/environmental exposure.

4. Conclusion

The presented results show overall good dosimeter performance, in accordance with the standard requirements, as well as manufacturer-stated specifications. Some dosimeter models, both APD and AAD, exhibited excellent performance, having small variations in their response across the full dose rate and photon energy range. The results were also evaluated against newly proposed limits of variation for Class A dosimeters. Some of the novel and state-of-the-art APDs and AADs meet the stricter requirements for both tests, supporting the proposal for introducing two dosimeter classes. Additionally, presented results highlight the importance of dosimeter type testing since it represents the most important step in discovering any shortcomings related to dosimeter design. However, type testing is performed only on a small number of units. Calibration and/or verification can be used to ensure that each individual unit is working appropriately. In the case of dosimeters that are not type tested, extended calibration or testing is highly recommended. Type testing standards reflect both user requirements and technological progress, which is why they are regularly reviewed and updated. Therefore, data presented in this study could present additional input for harmonization and update of type testing standards in radiation protection dosimetry.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nikola Kržanović: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jelena Vlahović:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Miloš Đaletić:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Miloš Živanović:** Writing – review &

Fig. 8. Energy dependence of active ambient dosimeter (AAD) response, $n > 10$, in the range from 33 keV (N-40) to 1.25 MeV (S-Co), normalized to the S-Cs radiation quality (662 keV). a) AAD3; b) AAD6; c) AAD8; d) AAD10; e) AAD11; f) AAD30. The limits of variation (-29% ; $+67\%$) in terms of relative energy response are displayed (IEC, 2009).

Fig. 9. Energy dependence of active ambient dosimeter (AAD) response, $n < 10$, in the range from 33 keV (N-40) to 1.25 MeV (S-Co), normalized to the S-Cs radiation quality (662 keV): a) AAD1-18; b) AAD20-34. The limits of variation (-29% ; $+67\%$) in terms of relative energy response are displayed (IEC, 2009).

editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. Ivana Stojanović: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Data curation. Srboj Stanković:

Fig. 10. Energy response dependence of active ambient dosimeters (AAD), $n < 10$, which had pronounced response variation, in the range from 33 keV (N-40) to 1.25 MeV (S-Co), normalized to the S-Cs radiation quality (662 keV). The limits of variation (-29% ; $+67\%$) in terms of relative energy response are displayed (IEC, 2009).

Writing – review & editing. **Luka Bakrač:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Teemu Siiskonen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Reetta Nylund:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Paula Toroi:** Writing – review & editing. **Vladimir Sochor:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jana Šmoldasová:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Łukasz Michalik:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Argiro Boziari:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Ana Fernandes:** Writing – review & editing. **Margarida Caldeira:** Writing – review & editing. **Siarhei Saroka:** Writing – review & editing. **Maria do Ceu Ferreira:** Writing – review & editing.

Declarations of interest

None.

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